

Digitization of Public Services in the Republic of North Macedonia in the Context of the Digital Transformation of the EU in the period 2016-2023

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The EU documents in the period 2016-2023 in the field of public administration aim at a well-prepared administration that has the citizen at the center of its operations and quality digital delivery of services. States aspiring to be members of the union, including RNM, in the future period should implement the good practices of the EU and harmonize the law and policies in this part as well.

The digitalization of services in the EU is a trend that relies on Internet technology and improves the performance of the services received by citizens within the European Union.

The main goal of the paper is the selection and analysis of the EU documents for digital transformation of the public administration (declarations and action plans) in the specified period, as well as targeting the challenges in the digital transformation of public services in the Republic of North Macedonia.

Keywords: digitization, EU public administration, digital transformation, public services

INTRODUCTION

The administration of a country is a very important factor for overall social and economic development and a tool that benefits the citizen. Service orientation towards the realization of rights in everyday life should be a priority. Considering our aspiration for full membership in the European Union, it is necessary to take steps and reforms that lead to an efficient public administration that works according to European principles and standards.

Digitization means converting analog information into digital form and aims to provide equal access for every citizen to services, data and knowledge with the help of digital technology. Digitalization of public services, as a concept of action of the public administration and as a service to citizens should lead to faster, more efficient and responsive access to services. Digital transformation includes: modernization of work equipment and machines, development of new services and products, robotics and automation of processes, security and reliability of systems, quality control and employees¹.

The rapid development of internet technology and the Covid-19 crisis have given this process a central place in the next period as one of the EU's priorities as one of the union's top priorities for the period 2019-2024².

The purpose of this paper is to determine the positive legal regulation of the digitization process in RNM compared to digitization in the EU.

1. Digital transformation of public administration in RNM

In the Republic of North Macedonia, the establishment of the Ministry of Information Society and Administration in 2008 is considered to be the beginning of the concepts of e-government and e-services, with a special emphasis on the IT development of administration and services to citizens.

¹ Digital transformation, Masit Macedonia, Skopje, 2020 (p. 11)

² Political Guidelines of the Commission 2019-2024, https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024_en#documents

However, the adoption of the Strategy for Reforms in Public Administration in the period 2010-2015 is considered to be a real beginning, which places a special emphasis on e-Government and e-Governance in accordance with the National Strategy for the Development of Electronic Communications with Information Technologies³, there is also and Action Plan.

The Public Administration Reform Strategy 2018-2022 is coordinated by the Public Administration Reform Council. According to the goals set by this Strategy, the following results are expected⁴: depoliticized public administration and restored citizens' trust in the institutions; functional rule of law and rule of law; improved policies that will ensure development in all spheres of society; built structures and administrative capacities prepared for the negotiation process with the EU; institutionally reorganized and optimized public administration; created new and retention of professional and competent administrative officers; simplified and more efficient application of modern information technologies; responsible, accountable and transparent institutions, managers and employees; and Delivered quality services to citizens and businesses.

The latest Strategy⁵ valid for the period 2023-2030 together with an action plan for the implementation of digitization in the period 2023-2026 is in progress.

2. The digitalization of public services in the EU

When we are talking about the development of digitalization within the European Union (in the following text EU), we can determine an expansion of the digital environment and the great development of technology within the entities in the capacity of service providers have brought great benefits to businesses, citizens (parties), institutions and entrepreneurs. Thus were created digital administrative procedures, digital profiles and identities, data that are of great risk and exposure to various hacker attacks. Considering the great sensitivity, many legal solutions have been developed in order to increase the confidence of the citizens in the security of the systems.

The adoption of the Directive on services in the internal market⁶, which refers to service providers inside the union and refers to non-economic services, financial services, electronic

³ The strategy for reforms in public administration in the period 2010-2015, p.58

⁴ Public Administration Reform Strategy 2018-2022, February 2018 of the Ministry of Information Society and Administration

⁵ Public Administration Reform Strategy 2023-2030 with Action Plan 2023-2026, Ministry of Information Society and Administration, July 2023

communications, health services, etc., is considered as a beginning of the modernization of the public administration of the EU. This directive seeks to introduce a one stop shop or a single point of contact from where all the necessary formalities are provided for services to citizens in service activities.

As a continuation of the previous directive, the Regulation on electronic identification and confidential services for electronic transactions in the internal market⁷ is adopted, which lays the foundations for electronic identification, authentication, signing. "Electronic identification is the process of using personal identification data in electronic form that unequivocally represents either a natural or legal person or a natural person representing the legal person"⁸. The electronic signature represents digital data that is used to identify the user, and in addition, it establishes the authenticity of the document. The authenticity of the document is ensured by an electronic time stamp that confirms that certain data exists at the time of the document's issuance. The regulation, by unifying the legislation at the EU level, also contributes to the digitization of public administration, because in this context the use of electronic signatures, electronic stamps and electronic delivery is foreseen.

In 2018, the regulation was adopted to establish a single portal for access to information, procedures and services⁹, which makes the public administration transparent and open.

"Establishment and operation of a single gateway that allows citizens and businesses easy access to high-quality information, efficient procedures and effective support and problem-solving services in relation to Union rules and national rules applicable to citizens and businesses who realize or want to exercise their rights arising from the law of the Union in the area of the internal market"¹⁰.

In accordance with this regulation, the YOUR EUROPE¹¹ portal is being created for easy access to procedures:

⁶ Directive 2006/123/EZ of the European Parliament and the European Council on services in the internal market, Official Journal of the EU No. L376/36 of 27.12.2006

⁷ Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 July 2014 on electronic identification and trust services for electronic transactions in the internal market and repealing Directive 1999/93/EC

⁸ Article 3 of the Regulation, No 910/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 July 2014 on electronic identification and trust services for electronic transactions in the internal market and repealing Directive 1999/93/EC

⁹ Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 2 October 2018 establishing a single digital gateway to provide access to information, to procedures and to assistance and problem-solving services and amending Regulation (EU) No 1024/2012

¹⁰ Article 1 paragraph 1 of the Regulation on establishing a single portal for access to information, procedures and services, Official Journal of the European Union L 295/1 21.11.2018

¹¹ <https://europa.eu/youreurope/>

1. Related to birth, residence, study, work, migration, retirement and conducting business activities.

2. Related to travel, work, retirement, vehicle use, education, health care, consumer rights, data protection and others.

The Digital Services Act¹² contains the legal requirements to be applied to all digital services designed to provide products, services or content and protect digital rights.

The European Commission, through the digital services act, expects to fulfill three goals:

- To increase consumer protection and related basic digital rights.
- To promote a transparent and clear accountability framework on online platforms
- To encourage innovation, growth and competitiveness within the single European market

Within the framework of the union, as the most important procedures or prerequisites in this sphere, we would mention:

- Data protection (General Data Protection Regulation, ePrivacy Directive);
- Digital identity (eIDAS, EUid);
- Digital payment or transactions (BaFin, AML5, SEPBLAC, PSD2)

Data Protection (The General Data Protection Regulation)¹³ is an international law for the protection and security of personal data and came into force in the month of May 2018. This law applies to all legal entities or institutions to keep personal data secure. With GDPR, the EU strengthens the way to protect personal data and privacy, when already all citizens share their data with different applications, as a potential way for cyber attacks. Drastic penalties are foreseen for anyone who abuses privacy and security standards.

¹² Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on a Single Market For Digital Services and amending Directive 2000/31/EC (Digital Services Act) (Text with EEA relevance)

¹³ General Data Protection Regulation, REGULATION (EU) 2016/679 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL, of 27 April 2016, Official Journal of the European Union L 119/1 published 04.05.2016

Digital Identity¹⁴ came into force in 2016 and offers a secure framework for electronic interaction between the business sector, citizens and the public sector. As specific tasks, this system enables the creation of an electronic identity that is used within a country or within the Union, as well as enabling e-stamp, e-signature, etc. An agreement has currently been reached on a new legal framework for digital identity within the EU, to achieve the ultimate goal of full digitization of public services by 2030.

Digital payment or transactions within the EU is an important tool in the overall set of measures, which represents a set of measures and rules that enable the digital transaction of funds and electronic payment as well as fast, efficient and transparent payment (BaFin, AML5, SEPBLAC, PSD2).

Finally, near the end of 2022, the European Assembly and Council adopted a decision on Programs and policies of the Digital Decade 2030 with specific goals: to equip 80% of the population with digital skills, increase the number of IT experts to 20 million, enable 100% digital public services for citizens and the business sector, 100% of citizens have access to the electronic health system, 100% of EU citizens have digital identities, etc. All these goals are very ambitious and represent a model for RNM as a roadmap towards full digitization of services.

Declarations for digitization within the EU represent readiness and expressed will from the EU member states for the full implementation of the adopted legal acts. As declarations that have been adopted for the digitization of services are: the Tallinn Declaration on E-Government, the Berlin Declaration on Digital Society and Value-based Digital Government and as a result of the overall commitments and acts finally, during the month of January 2023, the European Declaration on digital rights and principles for the digital decade was adopted, which finally establishes the basic principles of the digital decade -2030 (digital transformation in the service of citizens; solidarity and inclusion; freedom of choice; right of access in the public digital space; security, protection and empowerment and sustainability).¹⁵

¹⁴ REGULATION (EU) No 910/2014 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on electronic identification and trust services for electronic transactions in the internal market and repealing Directive 1999/93/EC, Official Journal of the European Union L 257/73 EN, 28.8.2014

¹⁵ European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles for the Digital Decade, Official Journal of the European Union C 23/1, 23.01.2023

3. Legal aspects of the digitalization of services in the Republic of North Macedonia in the period 2016-2023

How are we doing with the digitalization of services in the Republic of North Macedonia, which is EU-oriented and of course accepts all principles and commitments and implements them in the work of the public administration? 2019 is the starting point for the start of the process towards full digitization of services in the public sector, when the following were adopted: the Law on the Central Population Register¹⁶, the Law on Electronic Management and Electronic Services¹⁷ and the Law on Electronic Documents, Electronic Identification and Confidential Services.¹⁸

The central population register is the basis for digital identification of citizens, through which one database is obtained for each individual and regulates the rights, obligations and responsibilities of all administrative bodies and all other legal and natural persons in RNM in relation to use and exchange of the data contained in the Central Population Register.¹⁹ The first processors of the population data are the Ministry of the Interior (personal identification documents) and the Ministry of Justice through the Directorate for Keeping Civil Records (certificate from the civil register of marriages, deaths and births), which is expressly provided for by Article 17 of the same law. The central population register is managed by the Ministry of Information Society and represents a basic database containing data on citizens. As for the registration process of each person in the points for e-Services, identification is carried out, with which the Individual Electronic Number of the Citizen (IENC) consisting of six digits, which also represents an electronic identity for each citizen, is registered.

As an important point, it should be mentioned the existence of a system of interoperability between institutions, which enables a safe exchange of information through established standards (as benefits of interoperability are: cooperation between institutions, data exchange, sharing and reuse of data, improved provision of public services, lower costs).²⁰

¹⁶ Law on Central Population Register, Official Journal of RNM, No. 98 of 05/21/2019

¹⁷ Law on Electronic Management and Electronic Services, RNM Official Journal, No. 98 of 21.05.2019

¹⁸ Law on electronic documents, electronic identification and confidential services, RNM Official Journal, No. 101 of 05/22/2019

¹⁹ Article 1 of the Law on the Central Population Register, RNM Official Journal, No. 98 of 05/21/2019

²⁰ Macedonian Interoperability Framework, Rajhideter P, Igor C., Manevski F., Josifovski N., https://mioa.gov.mk/sites/default/files/pbl_files/documents/Macedonian_Interoperability_Framework%20MIF_v2.0_mk.pdf (last accessed on 02.07.2023)

According to MIOA, until March 9, 2023, 53 institutions²¹ are included in the interoperability system, which means that all subjects who want to join the same platform need to submit a request, which requires meeting the necessary conditions and signing an agreement, which officially everything becomes part of the interoperability platform²². From the same institutions and legal entities that are included in the interoperability system, there are a total of 567 services that offer standardized data exchange, fast and efficient exchange, increased efficiency and effectiveness, easier access to data, reduced time for receiving a service, etc.²³

As a key law towards full digitization, the Law on Electronic Documents, Electronic Identification and Confidential Services²⁴, more specifically, Article 6 puts the electronic document on the same level as the original document drawn up in paper form, which equalizes the importance of the electronic document with the paper one and contributes to expansion and development of the digitization process. Furthermore, Article 7 of the same law mandates the creation of an electronic document, which already replaces the paper one and mandates working electronically. In the process of issuing an electronic document, it is preceded by the creation of an electronic certificate - the signature of the official, the electronic seal certificate, electronic delivery of the document, electronic storage of the document, etc., which enables the overall processing of electronic documents on one level system.

²¹ Central Communication Client of the Platform for Interoperability, Administration for Keeping Main book Registers, Basic Court Skopje 1, Macedonian Research Network, Employment Agency of RNM, FZOM (Fond for Health insurance of Macedonia), Basic Court Skopje 2, Central Register of RNM, State Bureau of Statistics, Ministry of Interior Works, Ministry of Labor and Social Policy, Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Ministry of Information Society and Administration, State Election Commission, Customs Administration of RNM, Ministry of Education and Science, Nextsens DOO Skopje, State Commission for Prevention of Corruption, Macedonian Telecom, PIOM (Pension and disability fund of Macedonia, UJP (Public Revenue office), Public Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Moldova, Directorate for Financial Intelligence, Agency for Management of Forfeited Property, Official Gazette of the Republic of Moldova, Agency for Real Estate Cadastre, Directorate for Financial Police, General Secretariat, NBRM (National Bank of the Republic of Macedonia), Ministry of Finance, Inspection Council, Eurotrust , Clearing House (Klirinshka Kukja), Ministry of Justice, Service Company RNM IT Macedonia, Regulatory Commission for Energy and Water Services, State Inspectorate of Agriculture, National Security Agency, Ministry of Transport and Communications, Ministry of Economy, Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management, Accreditation Institute, Ministry of Environment and Spatial Planning, Municipality of Aerodrom, Energy Agency and Food and Veterinary Agency (<https://mioa.gov.mk/?q=mk/node/1320> - accessed on 02.07, 2023)

²² Guidelines for connecting the interoperability platform (https://mioa.gov.mk/sites/default/files/pbl_files/documents/nasoki_za_povrzuvanje_na_platformata_za_interoperabilnost.pdf - accessed on 02.07.2023)

²³ <https://mioa.gov.mk/?q=mk/node/1320> and https://mioa.gov.mk/sites/default/files/pbl_files/documents/lista_na_aktivni_produkciski_web_servisi_3.pdf (last accessed on day 02, 07,2023)

²⁴ Law on electronic documents, electronic identification and confidential services, Official Journal of the RNM, no. 101 of 05/22/2019

With the development of the digitalization concept, the implementation of measures and tools began, the most important of which would be: a document management system in state administration bodies (DMS), a system for issuing digital certificates of public administration (PKI) or known as certificates for electronic signature (KIBS), interconnection and use of registers and databases between state authorities and institutions (interoperability), electronic identity cards (eID), electronic payment of administrative fees. With the help of the basic tools, digital services were also developed in special institutions such as: e-cadastre (<https://www.katastar.gov.mk>), e-tax (<https://etax-fl.ujp.gov.mk>) , e-portal/UVMK (<https://e-portal.uvmk.gov.mk>), complete e-treasury system (<https://etrezor.fzo.org.mk>), electronic system for public procurement (<https://www.e-nabavki.gov.mk>), e-application for employment in the public sector (<https://prijava.aa.mk>), electronic system for managing international permits for the transport of goods (<http://dozvoli-mtc.gov.mk/>), open data portal (<https://data.gov.mk/>), the only national electronic register of regulations of the Republic of Macedonia ENER, the National Portal for e-services (uslugi.gov.mk) as and establishment of One Point for Services (ETU) centers.

In view of the above, it can be seen that in the future, all measures and activities should be taken by the institutions to ensure full digitization of services. It is also necessary to keep pace with our allied countries from the EU, with which a partnership agreement was signed with Montenegro, North Macedonia, Albania and Serbia²⁵. Digital Europe²⁶ is a special driver of processes that are yet to take place in the field of digitization in the RNM, which have been adopted as priorities such as: Formation of a digitization agency, optimization of the central population register, improvement of digital services for persons with disabilities, increase of the number of online services, implementation of ICT Strategy, National Cyber Strategy, Strategy for reforms in public administration, etc.²⁷

CONCLUSION

The process of digitization of services in the Republic of North Macedonia is a very important tool and trend in highly developed countries for easier and more efficient provision of services for citizens, all the more so since after the Covid-19 crisis it was determined that digitization is an

²⁵ Second Regulatory Dialogue between the EU and the Western Balkans | Shaping Europe's digital future (europa.eu) (last accessed on 06.07.2023)

²⁶ Digital Europe Programme is the latest EU program that works to bring new digital technologies to the needs of business, citizens and the public sector. This program will support projects that focus on supercomputers, artificial intelligence, cyber protection, advanced digital skills and enabling of widespread use of digital innovations. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/activities/digital-programme> (last accessed on 06.07.2023)

²⁷ <https://digitalera.mioa.gov.mk/digital-transformation> (last accessed on 07/06/2023).

irreplaceable way to achieve their rights during similar pandemics and as such this process is of top priority.

Through the analysis of the work, it can be determined that the digitalization process faces many challenges such as: partial implementation of the reforms that are foreseen according to the strategies and action plans, inconsistency of the legal framework in individual institutions, problems with the technical framework (infrastructure), lack of trained staff and the like.

Analyzing the field of research, it can be concluded that serious efforts have been made in terms of changing the legal framework, through the adoption of several laws in 2019 such as the Law on the Central Population Register, the Law on Electronic Management and Electronic Services, and the Law for electronic documents, electronic identification and confidential services that comply ours with European legislation in the area of digitization and represent a legal framework for efficient and effective provision of services electronically, based on established standards and procedures. Here we would also mention the Law on the general administrative procedure, as well as the Law on archival operations.

The stagnation of the digitization process in certain institutions is also due to the independent procurement of IT equipment by each institution, as well as the development of e-solutions and the costs of maintaining them, which results in an irrational consumption of resources and possible abuse by them. The subject of analysis in this paper is the small number of services offered by the National Portal eServices (the total number of electronic services is 244, of which 105 are electronic services of the portal), for which it is necessary to increase the number of services in the future. Finally, the use of the interoperability platform by all institutions has been urged because it is in operation and the state invests significant resources in maintaining the hardware equipment and software solutions. Currently, there is a low utilization of the potential and only a few institutions actively exchange data within the platform. . This creates a non-proportionality between the costs of operation and the benefits that the platform offers.

As a big problem that needs to be solved is the lack of IT staff who lately are directed to the private sector due to the absence of a legal solution to allow them salaries that are competitive with the salaries that IT staff earn while working in other fields. In contrast to this, training of professional staff

with knowledge from all spheres of the administration for providing services to citizens is also necessary.

For a full and fast implementation of the digitalization process, political will is needed both at the central level and an increase in the cooperation of the Government and the local self-government for the joint implementation of the measures and at the same speed for the processes that lead to full digitalization. However, a key need for the development of e-solutions is to increase the budget funds that are available to the state authorities for the development of digital tools as a prerequisite for full digitization.

In view of the above and in view of the great benefits of digital services for all citizens, this process should be one of the leading and top priorities of government structures that often change, while the interest of citizens remains the same and receiving quality and fast services is from great importance for facilitating daily needs.

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